

Course of ICUC score and ICUC image documentation

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Today's evaluation of treatment usually relies on Patient Reported Outcome Measures (PROM).

ICUC adds a concise and reliable score and a documentation concept that allows retrospective analysis ([LIT injury](#) and [July Newsletter](#)).

Problem of clinical evaluation of treatment: The reliable evaluation requires undeniable recording that avoids technical performance bias.

Score: Is a tool for evaluation of a situation and its evolution in clinical practise or study. The score needs to be concise, specific and reliable to be continuously applied and cover the whole course.

- **Concise:** Undoubtedly defined questions and answers that are unfailingly understood.
- **Specific:** Oriented to the goal of treatment.
- **Reliable:** The procedure of collecting the information needs to be applicable so as to guarantee continuous data.

The **ICUC TT** score (Trauma Treatment) is: a tool to evaluate function limitations and pain.

The **ICUC TT** score is not: a compilation of questions vaguely related to the topic under discussion and with it clumsy to use: soon identified as inefficient and demotivating.

Functional Limitation according to patient	Pain
<p>0 Zero functional limitation. Can do any activity, as before fracture.</p> <p>1 Can do most activities. Some limitations of joint motion. Slight functional impairment.</p> <p>2 Can only do certain activities. Clear limitation of joint motion. Marked functional impairment.</p> <p>3 Unable to do most activities. Poor range of joint motion.</p> <p>4 Unable to do any activity. Stiff joint.</p>	<p>0 Zero pain</p> <p>1 Mild pain</p> <p>2 Moderate pain</p> <p>3 Intense pain</p> <p>4 Worst possible pain</p>
<p> Stable</p>	
<p> Worsening</p>	
<p>A perfect result is: Zero limitations and Zero pain</p>	

Examples:

1. Course of ICUC score in line with course of conventional documentation (Fig. 1 and Fig. 2).
2. Course of ICUC score not in line with x-ray course presently without additional information (Fig. 3).
3. Course of ICUC score not in line with x-rays and ROM with intra-operative ICUC documentation providing important additional information that may unveil the clue of the problem (Fig. 4).

Fig. 1: Course of ICUC score in line with course of conventional documentation. Uneventful course, patient reported outcome (pain, function and ROM) and x-ray in line. 65 year-old patient / ICUC® Post series.

Fig. 2: Course of ICUC score in line with course of conventional documentation. Uneventful course, patient reported outcome (pain, function and ROM) and x- ray in line. 70 year-old patient / ICUC® Post series.

Fig. 3: The evolution of the ICUC score (pain) is not in line with x-ray aspect. Current intra-operative ICUC documentation does exclude this documentation of surgical technology as unveiling the culprit. 30 year-old patient / ICUC® Post series.

Fig. 4: Intra-operative ICUC documentation provides important additional information that may unveil the clue of the problem (cf ICUC Newsletter Feb. 2017). Course of ICUC score may have helped to understand the case better.
ICUC® app ID: 22-OB-272.

REFERENCES

1. PATIENT REPORTED OUTCOME MEASURES.
2. PIETRO REGAZZONI, PETER V. GIANNOUDIS, SIMON LAMBERT, ALBERTO FERNANDEZ, STEPHAN M. PERREN. THE ICUC® APP: CAN IT PAVE THE WAY FOR QUALITY CONTROL AND TRANSPARENCY IN MEDICINE?
3. E. NELSON ET AL. PATIENT REPORTED OUTCOME MEASURES IN PRACTICE. PUBLISHED 10 FEBRUARY 2015. BMJ 2015;350:G7818.
4. D. BENNETT, B. HANRATTY, N. THOMPSON AND D. BEVERLAND: MEASUREMENT OF KNEE JOINT MOTION USING DIGITAL IMAGING. INT ORTHOP. 2009 DEC; 33(6): 1627–1631. DOI: 1007/S00264-008-0694-9.
5. ICUC.
6. ICUC JULY'S NEWSLETTER.
7. ICUC FEBRUARY'S NEWSLETTER.